

REFLECTION OF THE NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF
LANGUAGE IN TRANSLATION: CULTURAL DOMINANTS IN UZBEK
AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES OF THE XIX CENTURY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7481398>

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Annotation: *The national picture of the world in the language includes different specific constituents, while a person values connection between them and their parents, other human beings are concerned more about job and their future. Cultural assumptions distinctive from one person to another one, as cultural dominants for Uzbek and British people might differ a lot. However, there are similarities in the beliefs and values of the two nations.*

Key words: *cultural dominants differentiation, verabalization, language.*

When studying cultural dominants and their reflections in the language, we are following the ideas developed by V.I.Karasik, who specified the following criteria conditioning such classification:

- cultural dominants are conditioned by universal and specific aspects, while specific is usually represented by the differentiation in nomination of the objects and people's attitude towards them;
- the totality of value dominants forms a definite type of culture supported by and reflected in the language [4].

Taking into consideration these conditions, we selected the following cultural dominants that relate to the verabalization of the concept "Respect" in English and Uzbek linguocultures:

Scheme 4. Universal cultural dominants related to expressing “Respect” in English and Uzbek linguocultures in the XIX century

1. Family

Uzbek’s devotion to their family comes first. As every society has its leader, every family has its superior. According to Abdurauf Fitrat “Oila yoki oila boshqarish tartiblari” every nation has its cultural values and traditions. People live by following actual rules *“Bizga ma'lumki, odamlar qayerda qavm yoki qabila bo'lib yashasalar, tinchliklarini saqlash uchun va bir-birlarining huquqlarini muhofaza qilish uchun bir nizom (tartib) va qonun joriy etib, shu qonunlar asosida baxt va saodatga erishganlar”* [Fitrat; 2013, 5]. He states that in order to be happy people must obey traditional rules.

Politeness, respect, and kindness are good commands to have among each other. “*Sen*” as an informal pronoun might be used when the relative is younger than the speaker. For instance, aunts, uncles, grandparents express “*sen*” (you) to their nieces and nephews.

From the given above dialog it can be concluded that family values are the foundation to guide the society. They are created from the morals, integrity and rules on how people live.

2. Religion

Egam, ismingni aytmok jur'atin bergil zabonimga,

Ko'ngil - xomush sadaf, dur jilvasin bergil bayonimga [G'olib, 2013, 14].

In the above example, Mirzo Golib provides important information to the addressee. The poet addressing God, in his *“Egam, ismingni aytmok jur'atin bergil zabonimga”*, is asking permission to say God’s name, by asking this the author is showing gratitude and high respect [3].

It is not surprising that the concept of “*faith*” “*iymon*” is a fundamental characteristic of the Muslim mentality, displayed in Islam. *“And thus do We explain the Signs in various ways that the truth may become established and that*

they may say: “Thou hast read out what thou hast learned’ and that We may explain it to a people who have knowledge” [1].

There is an interpretation of the dominant features of the truth as an extraordinary synthesis of faith to another person (especially, friend) and society regarding respect in this way. So, Islam leads people to good deeds in order to achieve real happiness in life.

“Gave them help. And the Agarites were delivered into their hands, and all that were with them, because they called upon God in the battle: and he heard them, because they had put their faith in him” [2].

The word “*faith*” has a general personation of the mind that the certain statement is true.

Respect to nature is also observed in two liguocultures. For example, Shelley set most of his poems in autumn, themes such as beauty, passion, nature, creativity and liberty were under his pen [3]. The excerpted poem is characterized by a high degree of emotiveness, from the other hand the author implied words as “love”, “hope”, “heart” and “art” in order to attract reader’s attention to express respect to the mother nature and time.

“Love, Hope, and Self-esteem, like clouds depart

And come, for some uncertain moments lent [Shelley, 1816, 2].

By admiring the nature, Shelley emphasizes its role and importance for humanity. Explicitly, he claims that no one should attempt to change or harm it, however, a number of metaphors in this poem (*human thought art nourishment, Thou messenger of sympathies, dying flame, That wax and wane in lovers’ eyes*) make reader think about implicit connotations that elucidate the author’s respect to the nature.

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